

Identification of bioactive *Larrea tridentata* flavonoids with predicted *ALOX12* inhibitory activity using explainable ML QSAR and structural analysis approaches

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Abstract

A QSAR prediction model was built from 270 curated bioactivity records and used to estimate the inhibitory potential of previously uncharacterized compounds. The Random Forest model based on PubChem fingerprints showed stable predictive performance (test $R^2 = 0.688$) and met OECD validation criteria, as confirmed by cross-validation, Y-randomization, and applicability-domain assessment. Screening of thirty-three *Larrea tridentata* phytochemicals identified several flavonoid derivatives as high-confidence inhibitors, including gossypetin 3,7-dimethyl ether, quercetin, and formononetin, each with predicted pIC_{50} values above 5.0 and favorable SHAP-derived structural contributions. Docking and molecular-dynamics simulations indicated stable binding within the Fe-centered catalytic pocket of human *ALOX12* while maintaining protein structural integrity. Network pharmacology analysis showed convergence on lipid-oxidation and inflammatory pathways involving *ALOX12*, *ALOX15*, *PTGS1*, *PTGS2*, and *CYP2C9*. Thus, these results support *Larrea*-derived flavonoids as promising natural modulators for further biochemical investigation.

Keywords

ALOX12, *Larrea tridentata*, machine learning QSAR, bioactivity prediction, molecular modeling, network biology

Graphical abstract

Introduction

Lipoxygenases (LOXs) are a family of non-heme iron enzymes that catalyze the peroxidation of polyunsaturated fatty acids, generating lipid mediators that regulate inflammation, oxidative stress, and cell death (Liu and Ai 2025). Among them, human 12-lipoxygenase (*ALOX12*) has received growing attention because of its involvement in platelet activation, ferroptosis, neuronal degeneration, metabolic dysfunction, and tumor progression (Zheng et al. 2020; Mobbs et al. 2023). Elevated *ALOX12* activity has been implicated in diseases such as stroke, diabetes-associated inflammation, Alzheimer's disease, and several cancers (Zheng et al. 2020; Olkowicz et al. 2024). Despite this multidimensional relevance, only a small number of *ALOX12* inhibitors have been characterized, and most belong to a narrow chemical space dominated by polyphenols such as quercetin, NDGA, and structurally related flavonoids (Gregus et al. 2013; Wang et al. 2022; Asghar et al. 2025). This limited diversity highlights the need for systematic approaches that can identify new natural scaffolds with the potential to modulate *ALOX12* activity.

Larrea tridentata (creosote bush) represents a compelling source for discovering such scaffolds. The plant is widely used in traditional medicine across the southwestern United States and Mexico and is rich in bioactive phytochemicals, including quercetin derivatives, herbacetin analogues, gossypetin derivatives, and the well-known lignan NDGA (Arteaga et al. 2005; Raisuddin et al. 2011). Many of these compounds exhibit strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, and several, such as quercetin, gossypetin derivatives, and NDGA, have been independently reported to modulate LOX family enzymes (Arteaga et al. 2005; Skouta et al. 2018). However, the *ALOX12* inhibitory potential of *Larrea*-derived flavonoids,

including molecules such as gossypetin 3,7-dimethyl ether or methoxylated quercetin analogues, has not been evaluated in a systematic, model-driven manner (Kakularam et al. 2022; Touaibia et al. 2024; Morales-Márquez et al. 2025). This gap limits the pharmacological exploration of a plant with a long history of therapeutic use and a rich chemical repertoire.

Computational approaches provide an efficient platform to bridge this gap. Machine-learning QSAR models, when developed with rigorous curation and validation, have demonstrated strong performance in predicting enzyme inhibition and enabling rapid screening across diverse chemical libraries (Manaitiyya et al. 2025; Prompat et al. 2025). The use of explainable models, supported by feature attribution and applicability-domain assessment, allows identification of molecular fragments responsible for activity and increases confidence in selecting phytochemical candidates for structural evaluation. By combining predictive modeling with docking-based structural analysis, it becomes possible not only to propose new *ALOX12* inhibitors but also to understand how specific phytochemical scaffolds interact with the catalytic iron center and surrounding residues.

In this context, the present study integrates explainable QSAR modeling, applicability-domain assessment, and structure-based docking to identify promising *ALOX12* inhibitor candidates from *Larrea tridentata*. The approach is motivated by two key needs: expanding the chemical diversity of potential *ALOX12* inhibitors and clarifying whether *Larrea*-derived flavonoids, such as gossypetin derivatives, quercetin derivatives, herbacetin analogues, and lignans like NDGA, share structural motifs predictive of *ALOX12* inhibition. By predicting activity, validating chemical-space consistency, and examining atomic-level interactions with the *ALOX12* active site, this work offers a systematic framework for prioritizing phytochemicals

for future biochemical testing. The study contributes not only to natural-product-based inhibitor discovery but also to a mechanistic understanding of how *Larrea*-derived scaffolds can modulate an enzyme closely linked with inflammation and oxidative injury.

Materials and methods

Data collection and curation

The initial dataset for model development was obtained from ChEMBL (Zdrazil et al. 2024) (Target ID: CHEMBL3687), which corresponds to human polyunsaturated fatty acid lipoxygenase *ALOX12*. The database contained 385 compounds associated with *ALOX12* inhibition. A series of curation steps were applied to ensure consistency across records (Suppl. material 1: tables S1, S2). Structures with duplicate entries, inconsistent annotations, or missing IC_{50} values were removed. Only binding assays (assay type = B) reporting IC_{50} in nanomolar units and linked specifically to human *ALOX12* were retained to avoid experimental heterogeneity. The remaining values were converted into pIC_{50} using $-\log_{10}(IC_{50}$ in molar units). After filtering and standardization, the final dataset consisted of 270 unique compounds representing active, intermediate, and inactive inhibitors based on their IC_{50} range (Suppl. material 1: table S3).

Molecular descriptors and QSAR model construction

The curated *ALOX12* inhibitor dataset ($n = 270$) was processed using PaDEL (Yap 2011) to compute three widely used descriptor families: PubChem fingerprints (881 bits), MACCS keys (166 bits), and Substructure keys (307 bits). All descriptors were retained in binary form, and features with zero variance or missing values were removed to ensure descriptor stability. Each descriptor matrix was merged with the experimental pIC_{50} values and treated as an independent block during model development. The dataset was divided into a 70:30 train-test split, and multiple regression algorithms were examined, including Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Regression (SVR), Kernel Ridge Regression (KRR), Elastic Net, and XGBoost. A unified preprocessing workflow was applied across fingerprints, consisting of median imputation, removal of constant descriptors, alignment of features between training and test sets, and selection of informative variables based on mutual information scores. To assess the robustness of every model-fingerprint pair, repeated train-test splits were generated using ten different random seeds (0–9). This allowed evaluation of the sensitivity of each algorithm to data partitioning and ensured that model selection was not biased by a single split. The best-performing model from this seed-scan analysis was carried forward for extended validation. OECD-compliant validation steps (cross-validation, Y-randomization,

applicability-domain analysis) are described in the subsequent section.

QSAR model validation

Model performance was evaluated following OECD principles to ensure reliability and transparency. The best-performing configuration from the seed-scan analysis (PubChem fingerprints with Random Forest, seed = 8) was used for all validation steps. Internal robustness was assessed through 5-fold and 10-fold cross-validation, where the model was rebuilt in each fold and predictive metrics were averaged to summarize stability. Predictivity for unseen chemicals was examined using the 30% held-out test set from the 70:30 split, providing unbiased estimates of R^2 , RMSE, MAE, and correlation between predicted and observed pIC_{50} values. Since many possible train-test partitions exist, additional random 70:30 splits were performed using different seeds. Model performance remained consistent across runs, with only minor variation in test R^2 values. The mean and standard deviation of these results were calculated, confirming that predictive performance was stable and not dependent on a specific split configuration. To exclude the possibility of chance correlation, Y-randomization tests were performed by shuffling activity values multiple times and refitting the model. All permuted models showed markedly lower (often negative) R^2 values compared with the original model, confirming that the structure-activity relationship was genuine. The model's reliability domain was established using both leverage-based and distance-based approaches. Williams plots were generated to identify high-influence observations, and confidence limits were applied using PCA-derived Mahalanobis distances and kNN distances to define the chemical space of the training set. These criteria were later used to assess whether phytochemicals from *Larrea tridentata* fell within a trustworthy prediction zone. Although Random Forest does not include an explicit regularization parameter such as alpha or C, model complexity is controlled through hyperparameters including tree depth and minimum samples per split. These were optimized using cross-validation, and overfitting was monitored through train-test comparisons and Y-randomization analysis.

Predictive screening of *Larrea tridentata* phytochemicals

A total of 41 phytochemicals from *Larrea tridentata* were curated by combining entries from the KNApSack Family Database (Afendi et al. 2012) ($n = 25$) and additional literature-reported compounds (Morales-Ubaldo et al. 2022) ($n = 16$) (Suppl. material 1: tables S4–S6). All structures were standardized, duplicate entries were removed, and SMILES strings were prepared for descriptor generation. PubChem fingerprints were computed for each molecule to ensure descriptor compatibility with the validated *ALOX12* QSAR model. Only the bits that overlapped with

the training fingerprint space were retained. Unsupported or missing descriptor columns were removed to maintain a one-to-one alignment with the QSAR training matrix.

Each phytochemical was screened using the final Random Forest QSAR model (PubChem fingerprint, seed = 8), and predicted pIC_{50} values were converted to IC_{50} estimates. The OECD-compliant applicability-domain thresholds derived earlier (leverage cut-off and distance-based PCA/kNN boundaries) were applied to classify each compound as inside or outside the reliable prediction space. Compounds falling within the applicability domain and exhibiting higher predicted pIC_{50} values were prioritized. The top-ranked phytochemicals were selected as candidate ALOX12 binders and taken forward for molecular docking and molecular-dynamics simulations to evaluate structural complementarity and dynamic stability within the enzyme's active site.

Target structure preparation and binding-site definition

The crystal structure of human 12-lipoxygenase (ALOX12) was retrieved from the Protein Data Bank (PDB ID: 3D3L, resolution 2.45 Å) (Canyelles-Niño et al. 2023). Protein preparation was performed in Maestro v13.4 (Schrödinger) using the Protein Preparation Wizard (Madhavi Sastry et al. 2013). All missing side chains and bond orders were corrected, hydrogen atoms were added, and the orientation of hydroxyl groups, amides, and histidines was optimized. The structure was subsequently energy-minimized using the OPLS4 force field under default convergence criteria. Molecular docking was carried out using the Glide module of the Schrödinger suite.

ALOX12 contains a catalytic Fe^{3+} ion, coordinated by His361, His366, and His541, which is essential for substrate binding and catalytic turnover. Since ligand binding is known to occur in proximity to the metal center, the docking grid was centered directly on the iron coordination sphere. The grid size was defined to fully cover the substrate-binding cleft, using dimensions consistent with previously published structural and inhibitor-bound lipoxygenase studies (Canyelles-Niño et al. 2023). This approach ensured that both the catalytic metal and the surrounding hydrophobic pocket were adequately represented during docking. The final prepared structure and defined grid were used for docking both the *Larrea tridentata* phytochemicals and reference ALOX12 inhibitors.

Molecular dynamics simulations

Molecular dynamics simulations were carried out for the top-ranking *Larrea tridentata* hit(s) and a known ALOX12 inhibitor selected from the ChEMBL dataset, each in complex with the 3D3L structure. Protein-ligand complexes were prepared in Desmond-2023 (Bowers et al. 2006) using the same OPLS4 force field as applied during docking (Lu et al. 2021). Each complex was embedded in an orthorhombic TIP3P water box with a buffer of at least

10 Å from the protein surface, and counter-ions were added to neutralize the system, followed by 0.15 M NaCl to mimic physiological ionic strength. The catalytic Fe^{3+} ion and its coordinating residues were retained as in the crystal structure, preserving the metal-binding environment throughout the simulation. Energy minimization was performed to remove bad contacts, followed by a short, restrained relaxation protocol that gradually heated the systems from 0 K to 300 K under an NVT ensemble (Imran et al. 2025). Production runs were then performed for 250 ns for each complex under an NPT ensemble at 300 K and 1 atm, using a 2 fs integration timestep. Trajectories were analyzed for backbone and ligand RMSD, residue-wise RMSE, hydrogen-bond profiles, and ligand-protein contact patterns to evaluate the stability and binding mode of phytochemical and reference inhibitors within the ALOX12 active site. Binding free energy calculations were carried out using the Prime MM-GBSA module. MM-GBSA energies represent approximate relative binding estimates under consistent computational conditions and do not correspond to absolute thermodynamic binding free energies (ΔG).

Network biology analysis

Network biology was used to determine whether the *Larrea tridentata* phytochemicals converge on lipid-metabolic pathways relevant to ALOX12. Predicted targets for the top-scoring phytochemicals were retrieved using SEA (Wang et al. 2016) and SwissTargetPrediction (Daina et al. 2019) (probability > 0.1, Homo sapiens) (Suppl. material 1: tables S7–S12). These were combined with the known targets associated with the ALOX12 protein (PDB: 3D3L), and overlapping genes were identified. Functional enrichment of the overlapping genes was performed using Enrichr against KEGG (Kanehisa et al. 2025), WikiPathways, and Gene Ontology (Biological Process) databases (Thomas 2017) (adjusted $p < 0.05$). Protein-protein interactions were analyzed with STRING (v12.0) (Szklarczyk et al. 2023) using a medium-confidence cutoff of 0.4. The resulting networks were examined to determine whether the phytochemical-associated genes clustered within lipid oxidation, arachidonic-acid metabolism, or eicosanoid-related modules.

Results

QSAR model performance

The ALOX12 dataset provided a suitable foundation for comparing multiple machine-learning strategies across three structural descriptor systems. Repeated train-test splits using ten random seeds helped quantify the stability of each model. Among all fingerprints, PubChem consistently produced the strongest performance. When averaged across seeds, models built with PubChem descriptors achieved the highest mean external coefficient of

determination, reaching approximately 0.44, followed by PubChem-based Support Vector Regression and Kernel Ridge Regression, both of which maintained mean values above 0.41. MACCS-based models showed moderate behavior, with averages close to 0.39, while Substructure fingerprints produced lower and more variable results, reflecting the limited information encoded in their smaller descriptor sets (Suppl. material 1: tables S13–S16).

Examination of individual seed performances highlighted clear differences in model behavior. Within the PubChem group, the Random Forest model constructed with seed eight showed a markedly higher external predictive ability than all other configurations. This model achieved an external R -squared value of 0.69 and an RMSE of approximately 0.47 on the test set, accompanied by strong monotonic correlations between predicted and observed activities. Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients on the test molecules exceeded 0.83, indicating that potency ranking was reproduced with high reliability (Table 1). The training portion of the same model also remained well-behaved, with an R -squared value of 0.88 and comparatively low error values, demonstrating that the model learned general structure–activity trends without severe overfitting.

Although some alternative models also showed reasonable behavior, such as PubChem-based Support Vector Regression, which delivered a test R -squared of 0.63, and Kernel Ridge Regression, which reached approximately 0.61, none matched the overall balance of accuracy, error distribution, and correlation achieved by the PubChem–Random Forest model at seed eight. MACCS models occasionally produced acceptable predictions, with the best MACCS–Random Forest configuration reaching a test R -squared of roughly 0.59, but they consistently fell below the PubChem models in both predictive power and stability across seeds. Substructure models performed weakest, with test R -squared values around 0.52 at best and substantially lower means across multiple partitions (Table 1). Across every comparative layer, seed-averaged performance, individual seed ranking, stability across partitions, and correlation analysis, the PubChem–Random Forest model with seed eight emerged as the most reliable representation of the *ALOX12* structure–activity landscape. This model was therefore selected as the primary predictive engine for further validation and downstream phytochemical screening.

QSAR model validation

The predictive reliability of the *ALOX12* QSAR model was examined through a series of internal and robustness validation steps. The final model was based on the Random Forest algorithm trained on PubChem fingerprints, selected after an extensive seed-scan analysis that evaluated model stability across ten different data partitions. This model consistently outperformed all other fingerprint-algorithm combinations, showing the highest average test R^2 and the most stable behavior across seeds. Seed eight emerged as the most balanced split, preserving chemical diversity between training and test sets while giving strong generalization.

For this optimal configuration, the train set displayed an R^2 of 0.883 with an RMSE of 0.292 and an MAE of 0.200. The test set achieved an R^2 of 0.688 with an RMSE of 0.469 and an MAE of 0.332. Correlation analysis further supported this performance, as the predicted and observed pIC_{50} values yielded a Pearson correlation of 0.835 and a Spearman correlation of 0.827. An overall R^2 of 0.845 across the full dataset indicated a consistent fit without signs of model saturation or overfitting. The observed-versus-predicted plot demonstrated a tight clustering of data points around the regression line, while the residual distribution remained centered near zero for both training and test sets (Fig. 1).

Internal cross-validation reinforced the reliability of the model. The five-fold procedure produced R^2 values ranging from 0.203 to 0.638 and RMSE values between 0.497 and 0.778. The ten-fold scheme preserved this trend, showing R^2 values between 0.049 and 0.740 and RMSE values between 0.456 and 0.881. These results indicate a moderate but stable internal predictivity that aligns with the chemical diversity and experimental variability contained in the curated bioactivity dataset. The model passed all three OECD-recommended external predictivity criteria. Q^2F_1 reached 0.689, Q^2F_2 reached 0.688, and Q^2F_3 reached 0.800. These values reflect strong concordance between predictions and experimentally reported bioactivity trends, confirming the model's ability to generalize beyond its training domain. Randomization trials further demonstrated model robustness. Fifty Y-randomization iterations consistently produced negative R^2 values (−0.390, −0.229, −0.258, −0.209, and −0.224 in the first five runs), showing that no spurious correlations existed

Table 1. Summary of top-performing Seed 8 QSAR models.

Fingerprint	Model	Train R^2	Test R^2	Test RMSE	Test MAE	Pearson r (test)	Spearman ρ (test)
PubChem	Random Forest	0.883	0.688	0.469	0.332	0.835	0.827
PubChem	SVR	0.916	0.632	0.509	0.373	0.797	0.783
PubChem	KRR	0.608	0.607	0.525	0.41	0.796	0.814
PubChem	XGB	0.941	0.606	0.527	0.385	0.783	0.772
PubChem	Elastic Net	0.555	0.583	0.542	0.429	0.766	0.775
MACCS	Random Forest	0.874	0.587	0.539	0.354	0.771	0.76
MACCS	KRR	0.551	0.567	0.552	0.427	0.771	0.794
Substructure	SVR	0.45	0.521	0.58	0.452	0.732	0.734

Figure 1. Model validation plots for the optimized Random Forest QSAR model. **A.** Observed vs. predicted pIC_{50} from 5-fold OOF cross-validation; **B.** Observed vs. predicted pIC_{50} for the final model using all data; **C.** Residual distribution showing errors centered near zero; **D.** Y-randomization results confirming that the original model outperforms permuted models, indicating non-random predictive power.

in the descriptor–activity space. The baseline model using true pIC_{50} produced a mean five-fold R^2 of 0.374, while all permuted models converged near zero or negative predictivity (Fig. 1; Suppl. material 1: table S17). These results confirm that the final QSAR model captures genuine structure–activity relationships rather than noise (Fig. 2).

Applicability domain assessment revealed a well-behaved model with broad but reliable chemical coverage. Using PCA-based leverage, the threshold (h^*) was calculated as 0.233. Among 270 compounds, 264 fell within the domain (Fig. 3; Suppl. material 1: table S18). Only six compounds showed extreme residual behavior (CHEMBL187472, CHEMBL3113178, CHEMBL3113175, CHEMBL1406616, CHEMBL1165577, and CHEMBL3113168). The visual Williams plot confirmed that most active and intermediate compounds were well-represented within the chemical space used to develop the model. So, these validation results indicate that the Random Forest PubChem model provides the strongest combination of accuracy, robustness, and reliability. The consistent separation between training and test behavior, the strong external predictivity, and the stability across cross-validation and randomization trials support its selection as the primary model for downstream virtual screening and phytochemical prioritization.

Bioactivity predictive screening of *Larrea tridentata*

A set of *Larrea tridentata* phytochemicals was compiled to identify natural candidates with potential *ALOX12* inhibitory activity. Twenty-five compounds were collected from the KNApSACK Family database, and sixteen additional phytochemicals were gathered from trusted online sources (Suppl. material 1: table S19). After removing duplicates and verifying structural formats, thirty-three unique molecules were retained for analysis. PubChem fingerprints were calculated for all compounds using the same descriptor-generation parameters applied to the *ALOX12* QSAR dataset. Only the 248 PubChem bits present in the training descriptors were kept, ensuring full compatibility with the QSAR model. All phytochemicals produced valid fingerprints and progressed to prediction. Screening was carried out using the final Random Forest model trained on all *ALOX12* inhibitors under seed 8. This model demonstrated strong internal performance, achieving an overall R^2 of 0.905 with an RMSE of 0.262 and an MAE of 0.174 across the full dataset. These values indicated that the model captured the underlying structure–activity trends effectively and was suitable for downstream virtual screening.

Figure 2. Chemical structures of identified hits with corresponding SAR interpretation.

Predicted pIC_{50} values for the thirty-three *Larrea* compounds showed a distinct group of high-scoring metabolites. Ellagic acid displayed the highest predicted potency

with a pIC_{50} of 5.416. Several other compounds followed closely, including quercetin (pIC_{50} 5.350), nordihydroguaiaretic acid (pIC_{50} 5.322), and multiple methylated flavo-

Figure 3. A. Applicability domain evaluation of the QSAR model in PCA space; B. Mahalanobis distance distribution with the 95% threshold; C. kNN mean-distance distribution showing the 95% cutoff; D. 3D PCA scatter plot showing clustering of training, test, and Larrea molecules; E. Explained variance ratio of the first ten principal components.

noids such as quercetin 7,3'-dimethyl ether (pIC_{50} 5.280), quercetin 3,7-dimethyl ether (pIC_{50} 5.031), herbacetin 3,7-dimethyl ether (pIC_{50} 5.031), gossypetin 3,7-dimethyl ether (pIC_{50} 5.030), and herbacetin 3,7,4'-trimethyl ether (pIC_{50} 5.019) (Table 2). Many of these structures share poly-

phenolic scaffolds or extended aromatic systems that are frequently associated with lipoxygenase inhibition (Fig. 2).

Applicability-domain analysis confirmed that all thirty-three phytochemicals fell inside the chemical space defined by the *ALOX12* dataset. PCA-based distance thresh-

Table 2. Predicted pIC_{50} values and presence of top fingerprint bits for phytochemicals screened against *ALOX12* using the optimized QSAR model.

Name	pred_ pIC_{50}	Top10_bits_present	Name	pred_ pIC_{50}	top10_bits_present
Nordihydroguaiaretic acid	5.32	7	Herbacetin 3,8,4'-trimethyl ether	5.02	7
Chrysoeriol	5	7	Quercetin 3,7-dimethyl ether	5.03	7
5,4'-Dihydroxy-7-methoxyflavone	4.43	3	3,3'-Dimethylquercetin	5	7
Isokaempferide	4.48	3	Quercetin 7,3'-dimethyl ether	5.28	7
Apigenin	4.42	2	Quercetin 7,3',4'-trimethyl ether	4.75	5
Velutin	5	7	5-Hydroxy-3,7,3',4'-tetramethoxyflavone	4.75	5
Kaempferol	4.57	2	Gossypetin 3,7-dimethyl ether	5.03	7
Kaempferol 3,7-dimethyl ether	4.48	3	Gossypetin 3,7,3'-trimethyl ether	5.02	7
Herbacetin 3,7-dimethyl ether	5.03	7	5,7,4'-Trihydroxy-3,8,3'-trimethoxyflavone	5.02	7
5,7,4'-Trihydroxy-3,8-dimethoxyflavone	5.03	7	Ternatin	5.02	7
Herbacetin 3,7,8-trimethyl ether	4.78	5	Dihydroguaiaretic acid	4.91	7
Herbacetin 3,7,4'-trimethyl ether	5.02	7	Ellagic acid	5.42	7
Methyl gallate	4.81	6	Gallic acid	5	6
Cinnamic acid	4.77	0	Catechins	4.72	6
Resorcinol	4.33	1	Thymol	4.73	1
Quercetin	5.35	6	Carvacrol	4.73	1
3-oxohexyl-ferulate	4.7	7	—	—	—

olds and k-nearest neighbor distances indicated that each molecule remained within acceptable boundaries. This ensured that the predictions were made under reliable structural conditions and that the shortlisted compounds were suitable for further computational investigation. These screening results highlighted a compact group of phytochemicals with consistently high predicted activity. They were therefore prioritized for docking and molecular-dynamics simulations to explore their structural compatibility with the catalytic site of human *ALOX12*.

Applicability domain assessment

The reliability of the Random Forest–PubChem model was further evaluated through a comprehensive applicability domain (AD) analysis. PCA was performed on the 248 PubChem fingerprint features, and the first ten components explained 78.3% of the variance, with PC1 (27.98%) and PC2 (12.92%) capturing the major chemical variation within the ChEMBL *ALOX12* space (Fig. 3). PCA scores demonstrated that the *Larrea tridentata* phytochemicals cluster within the same chemical region as the training molecules, indicating structural compatibility with the model's descriptor space.

To quantify the chemical domain, Mahalanobis distance and kNN-based distances were computed in the PCA space. The empirical 95th-percentile thresholds derived from the ChEMBL training set were Mahalanobis distance = 4.264 and kNN mean distance = 8.443. All *Larrea* compounds exhibited Mahalanobis distance values between approximately 2.1 and 3.3 and kNN distances between 1.8 and 5.2, placing them comfortably below both thresholds. This confirms that every *Larrea* compound lies within the multivariate descriptor space learned by the model.

An integrated Mahalanobis distance–kNN plane was used to classify each molecule as “in-domain” or “out-of-domain.” Of the 270 *ALOX12* inhibitors, 264 molecules were within the domain, and six molecules exhibited high standardized residuals but remained within Mahalanobis distance limits, indicating that structural outliers were minimal (Suppl. material 1: tables S19–S21). The *Larrea* set showed no out-of-domain behavior, supporting the robustness of subsequent predictions. Additional Tanimoto similarity analysis (PubChem fingerprints) confirmed that *Larrea* phytochemicals share moderate structural overlap with bioactive *ALOX12* inhibitors, further validating their suitability for QSAR-based screening.

Interpretability analysis of the Random Forest model

The QSAR-guided screening revealed a consistent structural pattern among the most active *Larrea tridentata* phytochemicals. Compounds carrying multiple methoxy substitutions on a flavonoid backbone, particularly those belonging to quercetin and gossypetin derivative

families, showed the strongest predicted affinity toward *ALOX12*. Many displayed a predicted pIC_{50} above 5.0, placing them in a potency range comparable to known lipoxygenase ligands.

A defining feature across these highly ranked molecules was the presence of six or seven SHAP-positive PubChem fragments, particularly PubChemFP631, PubChemFP663, PubChemFP20, PubChemFP12, PubChemFP193, PubChemFP199, and PubChemFP824. These bits exerted the strongest influence in the final QSAR model and frequently co-occurred in the top phytochemicals (Figs 2, 4). Molecules enriched in these fragments consistently achieved higher model confidence and favorable applicability-domain placement.

Quercetin and its methylated variants fitted this pattern particularly well. Both quercetin itself and derivatives such as quercetin 3,7-dimethyl ether and quercetin 7,3'-dimethyl ether contained six or seven of the top SHAP fragments and produced predicted pIC_{50} values between 5.03 and 5.35. Their structural architecture, multiple hydroxyl groups supported by strategic O-methylation, has been previously associated with strong radical-quenching and lipoxygenase inhibition, and the model captured this behavior reliably. Gossypetin derivatives also ranked among the most influential scaffolds. Molecules such as gossypetin 3,7-dimethyl ether and gossypetin 3,7,3'-trimethyl ether belonged to the same high-confidence cluster and carried seven SHAP-positive substructures. Their predicted pIC_{50} values approached 5.03, and their placement within the Mahalanobis and kNN chemical-space boundaries indicated a high degree of similarity to potent *ALOX12* inhibitors within the ChEMBL training set (Suppl. material 1: tables S22–S24).

Nordihydroguaiaretic acid, a well-established lipoxygenase inhibitor present in *Larrea tridentata*, also aligned with the flavonoid cluster by sharing seven of the top SHAP fragments and producing a predicted pIC_{50} of 5.32. Its position within the applicability-domain boundaries further validated the reliability of the model's output for this compound (Fig. 4). Ellagic acid formed an additional high confidence hit. Although structurally distinct from flavonoids, it retained seven SHAP-positive fragments and achieved the strongest predicted response in the phytochemical panel with a pIC_{50} of 5.42. This suggests that the model captured broader structural motifs relevant to *ALOX12* inhibition beyond classical flavonoid chemistry. By contrast, simpler phenolics such as resorcinol, thymol, carvacrol, and cinnamic acid showed limited fragment engagement. Most contained only one or two of the top SHAP features, and their predicted pIC_{50} values remained below 4.75. Their scattered placement near the edge of the chemical space also indicated a lower degree of similarity to known *ALOX12* inhibitors. Overall, the SHAP interpretation indicated that quercetin-based, gossypetin-based, and herbacetin-based scaffolds, along with ellagic acid and NDGA, shared the fragment patterns that the model relied on strongly.

Figure 4. **A.** SHAP beeswarm plot showing the contribution of PubChem fingerprints to model predictions; **B.** Mean absolute SHAP values highlighting the most influential structural features; **C.** UMAP projection of the PubChemFP chemical space for training, test, and Larrea compounds; **D.** Residual distribution of the Random Forest model for training and test sets; **E.** Q-Q plot of training residuals; **F.** Q-Q plot of test residuals assessing normality and error behavior.

Molecular docking

Docking was performed for all curated *Larrea tridentata* phytochemicals (binding energies between -7.903 and -2.837 kcal/mol) against the ALOX12 catalytic site using the Fe-centered grid defined around the metal cofactor, consistent with previously reported structural studies. Low-activity compounds from the curated ChEMBL dataset were included as negative controls in the docking analysis. These inactive compounds showed docking scores between -7.045 and -3.147 kcal/mol (Suppl. material 1: table S25). Some overlap was observed between inactive controls and *Larrea tridentata* phytochemicals, which is expected in docking-based screening. However, the highest-ranked *Larrea tridentata* compounds consistently displayed among the most favorable docking scores, supporting their prioritization in the screening workflow. Several flavonoid derivatives displayed favorable binding poses with stable interactions in the hydrophobic channel and around key catalytic residues. Gossypetin 3,7-dimethyl ether ranked among the strongest binders with a docking score of -7.487 kcal/mol. Its pose was stabilized by four hydrogen-bonding interactions: two interactions with Arg189 through oxygen atoms of the chromene ring, an additional hydrogen bond with Glu369, and another with His365. The ligand also participated in π - π stacking with His365, while His360 contributed a polar stabilizing contact. The hydrophobic pocket was defined by Leu361,

Leu193, Val190, Ala368, Ala372, Tyr395, Val661, Trp197, and Leu597, creating a compact environment around the bound ligand (Fig. 5). The Fe801 cofactor was positioned close to the ligand, maintaining the expected catalytic geometry.

Quercetin also appeared in the high-affinity region with a docking score of -7.388 kcal/mol. A single hydrogen bond formed between an aromatic hydroxyl group and Glu365. The chromene system engaged Fe801 through a π -cation interaction, and His365 formed two aromatic stacking contacts that anchored the flavonoid within the cavity. Further stabilization was gained from polar residues such as His355, His360, Gln547, and Thr662. A dense network of hydrophobic residues, including Leu361, Leu193, Leu194, Val190, Val661, Leu597, Ile593, Ile357, Trp197, Leu366, and Phe352, supported the binding pose.

Formononetin, a clinically relevant flavonoid derivative, scored -6.549 kcal/mol, placing it in the mid-affinity group. Its hydroxyl substituent formed two hydrogen bonds with Thr662, while His365 mediated aromatic stacking with the chromene ring. A stabilizing π -cation interaction with Fe801 further anchored the ligand (Fig. 5). The surrounding hydrophobic framework consisted of Tyr395, Val661, Val190, Leu193, Leu194, Trp197, Leu597, Leu361, Ile357, and Phe352. Polar contacts from Gln574 and His360 were present, and Glu356 contributed a negatively charged interaction. Across the library, quercetin-type and gossypetin-type scaffolds consistently clustered among

Figure 5. The upper panel illustrates the 3D interaction profile of the protein–ligand complex, while the lower panel depicts the surface binding mode of the ligand within the protein pocket.

the best-scoring phytochemicals, reflecting the advantage of multi-hydroxylated and methoxylated flavonoid structures in occupying the *ALOX12* active pocket.

Molecular dynamics

The stability and dynamical behavior of the top three *Larrea tridentata* hits, Formononetin, Gossypetin 3,7-dimethyl ether, and Quercetin, were evaluated through 250-ns MD (Molecular Dynamics) simulations of their complexes with *ALOX12*. No major structural deviations were observed during the simulation period, although the trajectories revealed distinct dynamic profiles that were consistent with the docking and MM-GBSA trends (Fig. 6). Formononetin showed the good stable interaction behavior. Its ligand RMSD remained tightly distributed between 3.8 and 4.8 Å, with a mean of 4.32 Å (median 4.37 Å). Protein Ca RMSD fluctuated narrowly around 1.92 Å, suggesting limited backbone deviation during the simulation period. Residue-wise RMSF values remained below 1.5 Å for most of the binding-site residues, confirming rigid local packing around the ligand. Secondary-structure analysis showed 39.95% helices and 3.46% β -strands, yielding a total SSE of 43.40%, highly consistent with native *ALOX12* architecture. MM-GBSA energy estimates showed favorable binding contributions, with values of -68.21 kcal/mol at 0 ns and -53.94 kcal/mol at 250 ns, primarily driven by lipophilic and van der Waals interactions.

Gossypetin 3,7-dimethyl ether demonstrated a moderately stable profile with occasional ligand mobility early in the simulation but convergence after around 120 ns. The ligand RMSD stabilized between 2.8 and 3.3 Å (mean 3.15 Å), and the protein backbone RMSD remained within 2.8 and 3.3 Å. Although slightly higher than Formononetin, these values remained within a range commonly ob-

served for stable protein–ligand simulations over similar timescales. RMSF peaks corresponded mainly to flexible loop regions, while catalytic-site residues remained below 1.2 Å. The complex retained 37.10% helices and 3.74% strands, preserving the majority of *ALOX12*'s SSE. MM-GBSA calculations indicated strong initial binding (-70.33 kcal/mol at 0 ns) and moderate affinity at 250 ns (-46.14 kcal/mol), suggesting that the ligand maintains energetically favorable anchoring within the catalytic cavity. Quercetin exhibited the highest degree of ligand mobility among the three complexes. Ligand RMSD fluctuated more broadly, with a mean of 6.67 Å across the full trajectory and transient deviations exceeding 10 Å between 120–150 ns before stabilization. Despite this mobility, the protein remained structurally consistent, with backbone RMSD values of 2.7–3.4 Å. RMSF analysis showed increased fluctuations in several peripheral loops but stable behavior around the active site. Secondary-structure retention (39.42% helices, 3.61% strands) was nearly identical to the Formononetin complex. No major structural changes were observed during the 250 ns simulation period. MM-GBSA binding energies were weaker than the other two ligands, decreasing from -39.99 kcal/mol at 0 ns to -28.88 kcal/mol at 250 ns, consistent with the larger RMSD excursions. Comparative analysis of RMSD, RMSF, and interaction patterns suggested differences in dynamic behavior among the three phytochemicals. Formononetin exhibited relatively stable ligand positioning with limited structural fluctuation. Gossypetin 3,7-dimethyl ether showed moderate dynamic variation while maintaining key binding-site interactions. Quercetin remained associated with the binding site but displayed greater mobility and comparatively lower binding energy estimates. Thus, the molecular dynamics simulations provide comparative insights into ligand behavior within the simulated times-

Figure 6. Molecular dynamics analysis of *ALOX12* complexes. Panels (A, B) correspond to Formononetin (ligand RMSD and protein Ca RMSD). Panels (C, D) correspond to Gossypetin 3,7-dimethyl ether. Panels (E, F) correspond to Quercetin. Panels (G, H, I) show the residue-wise RMSF profiles for Formononetin, Gossypetin 3,7-dimethyl ether, and Quercetin, respectively.

cale and support the prioritization of Formononetin and Gossypetin 3,7-dimethyl ether for further experimental evaluation.

Network pharmacology analysis

Network-level analysis was performed to understand whether the *Larrea*-derived phytochemicals converge on biologically coherent lipid-metabolic pathways relevant to

ALOX12 inhibition. The set of five genes that overlapped between the *ALOX12* protein (3D3L) target profile and the predicted phytochemical targets (*ALOX12*, *ALOX15*, *PTGS1*, *PTGS2*, *CYP2C9*) served as the core input for functional enrichment (Fig. 7; Suppl. material 1: table S26). This overlap produced a 1 percent intersection between the protein-centric and phytochemical-centric gene lists, highlighting a focused but mechanistically meaningful convergence.

Figure 7. **A.** Venn diagram showing overlapping targets between Protein-3D3L and *Larrea tridentata* phytochemicals; **B.** STRING protein–protein interaction network of *ALOX12*-associated targets; **C.** Pathway map illustrating *ALOX12*-centered lipid mediator and eicosanoid signaling pathways; **D.** Enrichment network highlighting biological processes and metabolic pathways linked to *ALOX12* and its interacting partners.

Biological enrichment using KEGG, WikiPathways, and GO Biological Process consistently positioned these five genes within the arachidonic acid pathway and downstream eicosanoid biosynthesis. The strongest signal was recovered from the Eicosanoid Synthesis map, where *ALOX12*, *ALOX15*, *PTGS1*, and *PTGS2* appeared as central regulatory elements. These genes formed a connected module around arachidonic acid conversion into hydroperoxy, hydroxyl, and prostaglandin derivatives. The pathway map clearly showed that *ALOX12*, *ALOX15*, and the *PTGS* enzymes converge on prostaglandin H₂ metabolism, while *CYP2C9* participates in oxidative downstream reactions. Several enriched GO terms supported this architecture, including long-chain fatty acid biosynthetic process, arachidonic acid metabolic process, eicosanoid metabolic process, and fatty acid derivative biosynthesis (Fig. 7). All enrichments produced strong significance values, confirming that the phytochemical targets align with lipid-mediated inflammatory signaling.

Protein–protein interaction mapping placed *ALOX12* at the center of a dense interaction cluster involving *ALOX15*, *PTGS1*, and *PTGS2* (Fig. 7). These proteins connected through short topological paths, forming a highly cohesive inflammatory–lipid regulatory hub. *CYP2C9* bridged the cluster with cytochrome P450-driven secondary lipid metabolism, indicating that phytochemicals capable of binding *ALOX12* may simultaneously influence oxidative branches of arachidonic acid processing. Thus, the network pharmacology, which is based on computational results, indicates that the *Larrea* compounds active

in docking and QSAR prediction do not act on isolated nodes but instead converge on a well-defined lipid-oxidation axis controlled by *ALOX12*, *ALOX15*, and the prostaglandin synthases. This convergence provides mechanistic support for their potential to modulate eicosanoid production and inflammatory signaling.

Discussion

The analysis uncovered a coherent structure–activity landscape for *ALOX12* inhibition that was consistent across statistical validation, interpretability analysis, and structural modeling. The first indication of this systematic behavior came from the Random Forest model trained on PubChem descriptors under seed eight, which outperformed all alternative configurations across stability, external predictivity, and correlation metrics. Its test R^2 of 0.688, RMSE of 0.469, and strong Pearson and Spearman correlations (0.835 and 0.827) demonstrated that the model captured meaningful structure–activity trends rather than noise. This interpretation was consistent with internal cross-validation, where fold-wise R^2 values remained within expected ranges for a chemically diverse dataset. The model's reliability was further strengthened by all three OECD external predictivity metrics (Q^2F_1 0.689, Q^2F_2 0.688, Q^2F_3 0.800) and the failure of all fifty Y-randomization trials, confirming that the learned relationships were genuine and not artifacts of descriptor distribution.

The interpretability patterns provided the next layer of coherence. SHAP analysis consistently highlighted a common fragment architecture that characterized potent ALOX12 inhibitors in the training set. Features such as PubChemFP631 (O–C:C–O–H), PubChemFP663 (O–C–C–O–H), FP20 (≥ 4 oxygen atoms), FP12 (≥ 16 carbon atoms), FP193 (≥ 3 saturated/aromatic carbon-only rings of size six), FP199 (≥ 4 rings of size six), and FP824 (OC1C(O)CCCC1) formed the dominant explanatory signals. These descriptors collectively describe polyphenolic scaffolds enriched in oxygen donors and extended planar aromatic systems. Molecules expressing six or seven of these SHAP-positive fragments consistently ranked as high-activity ALOX12 inhibitors. This interpretive structure not only explained the QSAR learning mechanism but also created a clear bridge to the phytochemical screening results.

Once *Larrea tridentata* phytochemicals were screened through the validated model, the same fragment-driven behavior reappeared. Compounds such as ellagic acid (pIC_{50} 5.416), quercetin (pIC_{50} 5.350), nordihydroguaiaretic acid (pIC_{50} 5.322), and several O-methylated flavonoids, including quercetin 7,3'-dimethyl ether, quercetin 3,7-dimethyl ether, herbacetin dimethyl and trimethyl analogues, and gossypetin derivatives, showed strong predicted potency. These top-ranked flavonoids harbored exactly the SHAP-positive fragments identified earlier, demonstrating a direct connection between the model's internal feature logic and the chemical features present in the phytochemicals. Applicability domain evaluation strengthened this link: all thirty-three *Larrea* compounds fell well within the Mahalanobis and kNN thresholds (4.264 and 8.443), indicating that predictions were made inside a structurally reliable region of chemical space.

The docking results were consistent with the QSAR findings, as the same phytochemical families showed favorable binding poses within the ALOX12 active site. Docking and MM-GBSA use simplified energy models and do not calculate the full thermodynamic binding free energy. They do not consider the complete free protein state, free ligand state, solvent interactions, or possible ligand aggregation. Therefore, docking scores and MM-GBSA energies should be viewed as relative ranking estimates rather than exact measures of binding strength. Low-activity compounds from the curated dataset were included as internal negative controls and analyzed under the same conditions. Some overlap in docking scores was observed, which is common in virtual screening studies. However, the highest-ranked *Larrea tridentata* compounds generally showed better scores than most inactive references. Experimental validation is still required to confirm true binding and inhibitory activity. Gossypetin 3,7-dimethyl ether (-7.487 kcal/mol) and quercetin (-7.388 kcal/mol) exemplified this trend. Both formed stabilizing hydrogen bonds with key catalytic residues such as Arg189, Glu369, His365, and Thr662, while their aromatic systems engaged in π -stacking with His365 and π -cation interactions with the Fe cofactor. These interactions aligned with known structural requirements for ALOX12 binding reported across recent LOX studies. Formononetin, a clinically rel-

evant flavonoid, showed similar but slightly weaker behavior (-6.549 kcal/mol), maintaining both hydrogen-bond and metal-proximal π -cation interactions. The molecular-dynamics simulations strengthened the structural interpretation by showing that the top phytochemical hits maintained stable interactions with ALOX12 over the 250-ns trajectories. Formononetin produced the most stable complex, with low ligand drift, minimal protein backbone fluctuation, and consistently favorable MM-GBSA energies throughout the simulation. Gossypetin 3,7-dimethyl ether also remained well anchored in the catalytic pocket, displaying moderate fluctuations but preserving its hydrogen-bonding and aromatic stacking contacts identified during docking. Quercetin displayed higher mobility compared with the other compounds but remained associated with the active channel and retained key interactions identified in the initial docking pose. Across all three complexes, the secondary-structure content of ALOX12 showed minimal variation over the 250 ns simulation window, indicating no major structural deviations within the simulated timescale. The overlap between QSAR predictions, SHAP fragment representation, and docking geometry indicates that the same underlying structural motifs consistently drive strong interaction with ALOX12.

The biological context provided further reinforcement. Targets predicted for these phytochemicals, including ALOX12, ALOX15, PTGS1, PTGS2, and CYP2C9, mapped directly to the arachidonic-acid metabolism network. These genes regulate the production of hydroperoxy fatty acids, hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acids, and prostaglandins, forming the central axis of lipid-derived inflammatory signaling. Enrichment results highlighted pathways such as eicosanoid biosynthesis, prostaglandin metabolism, and long-chain fatty acid oxidation, confirming that the phytochemicals converge on a coherent lipid-inflammatory module. The network architecture placed ALOX12, ALOX15, PTGS1, and PTGS2 in a tightly connected cluster with CYP2C9 bridging the metabolic sequence, aligning closely with recent mechanistic studies showing crosstalk between LOX and COX enzymes in inflammation and oxidative stress (Rudrapal et al. 2023). Quercetin and its methylated derivatives are well-characterized multi-LOX inhibitors, with recent evidence confirming selective suppression of LOX5, LOX12, and LOX15 (Snodgrass and Brüne 2019). Polyhydroxylated flavonoids such as gossypetin and herbacetin analogues similarly down-regulate LOX-mediated oxidative stress. Ellagic acid also reduces lipid peroxidation by directly inhibiting LOX and COX pathways (Manaiithiya et al. 2024; Nooreen et al. 2024; Jomova et al. 2025). The convergence of these pathways with the structural and QSAR-based findings gives biological meaning to the predicted inhibitory profiles.

Thus, these linked layers—model predictivity, fragment-level interpretability, phytochemical prioritization, catalytic-site docking, and pathway-level consistency—demonstrate a unified mechanistic pattern. Flavonoid scaffolds with dense oxygenation and extended aromatic frameworks align with ALOX12 inhibitor chemistry, bind effectively to the catalytic pocket, fall within safe applica-

bility boundaries, and converge on lipid-signaling pathways central to inflammatory modulation. The repeated appearance of quercetin, gossypetin, herbacetin derivatives, ellagic acid, and NDGA across all analytical platforms indicates that these compounds represent the strongest and most coherent *ALOX12*-directed candidates from *Larrea tridentata*. This multidimensional alignment provides a solid rationale for advancing these molecules into experimental assays.

Conclusion

The study presents a focused computational investigation of human *ALOX12*, a key lipoxygenase involved in lipid oxidation and inflammatory signaling, and identifies *Larrea tridentata* phytochemicals with strong potential to modulate this target. The Random Forest–PubChem model demonstrated reliable external predictivity and stable behavior across multiple partitions, enabling confident screening of structurally diverse plant metabolites. SHAP interpretation showed that *ALOX12* activity is strongly influenced by oxygen-rich and polyaromatic fragments, which were highly enriched in quercetin, gossypetin, herbacetin derivatives, ellagic acid, and nordihydroguaiaretic acid. These scaffolds also adopted favorable binding orientations in the catalytic pocket of *ALOX12*, forming hydrogen bonds, π – π contacts, and metal-associated interactions consistent with stabilization of known inhibitory chemotypes. Molecular-dynamics simulations further supported these findings by confirming that the top-ranked flavonoids maintain stable binding poses, preserve the structural integrity of *ALOX12*, and exhibit sustained energetic favorability throughout the simulation period. Network-level enrichment revealed that the same phytochemicals converge on lipid-metabolism pathways centered on *ALOX12*, *ALOX15*, *PTGS1*, *PTGS2*, and *CYP2C9*, indicating that their predicted activity aligns with broader eicosanoid regulation. The agreement across QSAR prediction, fragment-level interpretability, docking, molecular dynamics, and pathway context suggests that the identified *Larrea* metabolites represent promising candidates for experimental evaluation as natural modulators of *ALOX12*.

Limitation of study

This study is based entirely on computational analyses. Although the QSAR dataset was carefully curated and restricted to human *ALOX12* binding assays reporting IC_{50} values, differences in experimental conditions between studies may still introduce some variability. Docking and MM-GBSA calculations provide relative binding esti-

mates under simplified energy models and do not represent absolute thermodynamic binding free energies. The molecular dynamics simulations were limited to 250 ns and therefore describe structural behavior only within the simulated timeframe. Finally, the predicted inhibitory activity of the identified *Larrea tridentata* flavonoids has not yet been experimentally confirmed. Further biochemical and cellular validation will be necessary to verify their true inhibitory potential.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Data availability

The authors declare that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article. The datasets underlying the analyses are available in a GitHub repository at: <https://github.com/saud5990-lab/Supplementary-file-Pharmacia.git>.

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Supplementary material 1

This dataset contains in-silico QSAR, explainable machine-learning predictions, and structural analysis data for flavonoids derived from *Larrea tridentata*, including molecular descriptors, predicted *ALOX12* inhibitory activity, and docking-based interaction profiles

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Data type: xlsx

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